

Deep Receiver Architectures for Robust MIMO Rate Splitting Multiple Access

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ABSTRACT Machine Learning tools are becoming very powerful alternatives to improve the robustness of wireless communication systems. Signal processing procedures that tend to collapse in the presence of model mismatches can be effectively improved and made robust by incorporating the selective use of data-driven techniques. This paper explores the use of neural network (NN)-based receivers to improve the reception of a Rate Splitting Multiple Access (RSMA) system. The intention is to explore several alternatives to conventional successive interference cancellation (SIC) techniques, which are known to be ineffective in the presence of channel state information (CSI) and model errors. The focus is on NN-based architectures that do not need to be retrained at each channel realization. The main idea is to replace some of the basic operations in a conventional multi-antenna SIC receiver by their NN-based equivalents, following a hybrid Model/Data-driven based approach that preserves the main procedures in the model-based signal demodulation chain. Three different architectures are explored along with their performance and computational complexity, characterized under different degrees of model uncertainty, including imperfect channel state information and non-linear channels. We evaluate the performance of data-driven architectures in overloaded scenario to analyze its effectiveness against conventional benchmarks. The study dictates that a higher degree of robustness of transceiver can be achieved, provided the neural architecture is well-designed and fed with the right information.

INDEX TERMS Convolutional neural network, deep learning, RSMA, symbol detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

MULTI-USER wireless systems have conventionally relied on *orthogonal* multiple access architectures to guarantee the correct multiplexing of signals associated to multiple transmitters/receivers. According to this conventional approach, different transmissions are supported by distinct orthogonal channels, typically following a time/frequency/space division multiplexing scheme. These architectures are very reliable from the performance perspective, but quite inefficient in terms of the potential supported rates. For this reason, recent approaches advocate for a more aggressive use of the available transmission resources, by essentially allowing different transmissions to superpose in the use of available transmit dimensions, that is by using

a *non-orthogonal* multiple access (NOMA) architecture. The main idea behind these approaches is to physically superpose different signals at the transmitter (superposition coding), which are then separated at the receiver via successive interference cancellation (SIC) techniques.

NOMA architectures can be effectively enhanced by multi-antenna technology at both transmitter and receiver (MIMO). In this context, it has recently been pointed out that Rate Splitting Multiple Access (RSMA), also a non-orthogonal transmission scheme, outperforms conventional NOMA architectures based on simple superposition coding [1], [2]. RSMA can be seen as a generalization of NOMA in multi-antenna settings, where superposition coding is effectively combined with precoding and where new

multi-cast symbol streams are also spatially multiplexed [3], [4]. RSMA has been pointed out as a unifying framework of existing MA schemes - OMA, SDMA and NOMA. RSMA enhances the benefits of multi-user MIMO (MU-MIMO) by achieving higher data rates and spectral efficiency, especially when users are closer together and under imperfect CSIT. A number of studies [2], [5], [6], [7] have demonstrated that RSMA shows a superior performance to the aforementioned MA schemes with respect to wide range of performance metrics - energy efficiency, robustness to different system loading, max-min fairness, among others. The interference management technique of partially decoding interference and partially treating the remaining as noise has received much attention for 6G [7], [8], [9], [10]. All these observations have led to the recommendation of 3GPP RAN to consider a study item on RSMA in Rel-19, which was outlined in 3GPP TSG RAN Rel-19 workshop [11], [12].

The simplest and most practical RSMA scheme is 1-layer RS, which is the basic building block of almost all existing RSMA architectures. It involves transmission of common message (common to all the users) followed by SIC and decoding of individual private messages (see Section II for details). Both NOMA and RSMA strongly rely on SIC at the receiver, which is the most critical signal recovery step in practical implementations. The presence of model imperfections (channel estimation errors, synchronization issues, RF imperfections, etc.) in the SIC operation leads to error propagation which significantly degrades the symbol detection performance. Perfect channel state information at the receiver (CSIR) is key for a correct SIC operation, and any degradation of the quality of CSIR can significantly impair its operation. Another important problem is the lack of perfect channel state information at transmitter (CSIT), which is more difficult to acquire in practice. The lack of perfect CSIT has an important effect on the precoder RSMA design, which ultimately leads to significant performance drop [13], [14], [15], [16]. At the transmitter side, [13] introduces a precoder design method, referred to as Sampled Average Approximation - Weighted Minimum Mean Square Error (SAA-WMMSE) which operates under known CSIT and CSIT error distribution. On the other hand, [15] and [16] evaluate MIMO rate splitting strategy with quantized and statistical CSIT. The studies related to imperfect CSIR for RSMA scenarios [17], [18], [19] highlight the sensitivity of precoding and symbol detection to channel state information. In [17], the estimated imperfect CSIR is assumed to be fed back via a lossless channel to the transmitter which affects the system capacity. The impact of CSIR estimation error on a model-based deep-learning (MBDL) receiver is considered in [19]. The performance of the proposed DL method is similar to that of conventional SIC receiver with imperfect CSIR, but the neural networks need retraining for each channel realization. In our paper, we will consider the use of neural networks to address both CSIT and CSIR effects without re-training for each channel. The use of carefully

designed data-driven schemes leads to improved robustness of the receiver operation.

Deep Learning (DL) approaches are particularly suitable in order to overcome limitations imposed by imperfections in CSIT, CSIR, and their effect on the SIC operation. For example, the work in [20] considers an uplink MIMO-NOMA scenario where deep neural networks (DNNs) are employed in a successive manner to decode the superposed symbol streams. Each original SIC step is replaced with a DNN, which results in the receiver requiring as many DNN blocks as the number of users in the system. On the other hand, [21] focuses on downlink NOMA and proposes the use of DNNs at both transmitter and receivers to jointly optimize the precoding and the symbol detection process. Each SIC step consists of two DNNs (one for decoding the symbol of preceding user, and the second to perform the actual SIC operation) making this approach computationally intensive. It is important to highlight that both approaches mentioned above require the neural networks to be trained for *each* channel realization, since the channel coefficients are not explicitly estimated. This is also the case of [22], which considers the use of DNNs for both SIC operation and symbol detection at the receivers in a NOMA downlink scenario. The DNN-based receiver outperforms the conventional SIC receiver with full CSIR, however channel conditions are assumed static during both the training and testing periods of the DNNs. Alternatively, [23] proposes to replace the entire receiver in a downlink MIMO-NOMA setting by a *single* neural network (NN) which is capable of decoding the symbols transmitted from all the transmit antennas in one shot. Here again, the proposed architecture requires alternating training and testing periods for each channel realization. Focusing specifically on the RSMA setting, [19] proposes the use of DNNs to replace specific blocks in the receiver, in order to efficiently decode common and private streams in the downlink. The issue of CSIR availability is addressed by comparing symbol detection against a conventional SIC receiver with imperfect CSIR. The importance of the system training overhead is highlighted by explicitly considering a *training sub-block* which consists of dedicated training symbols followed by data symbols to be predicted. Under the assumption of block fading channels and imperfect CSIR, the proposed approach outperforms conventional SIC receivers.

None of the above machine learning schemes consider channel estimation and symbol detection working in unison and, hence, the models need to be re-trained at each new channel realization. Note also that the number of pilot symbols needed to re-train the receivers in those studies is very high. For example, 960 or 5000 pilot symbols per channel realization are used in [20] and [22], respectively. For RSMA settings, 1280 symbols are needed e.g., in [19]. When DNNs are used to *jointly* optimize the transmitter and receivers in MIMO-NOMA setting [21], 10^5 symbols per channel realization are required. The use of data-driven architectures for channel estimation can eliminate the need

for such re-training, as shown in [24], [25], and [26] for other communication scenarios (e.g., massive MIMO, hybrid beamforming). In fact, both detectors and channel estimators can be trained offline once, and left frozen for the rest of the operation. This obviously results in a much lower training overhead compared to other data-driven approaches [19].

It should be pointed out that SIC receivers are not the only possible alternatives in RSMA receivers, especially when a forward error correction mechanism is implemented. In these situations, more complicated receiver architectures based on joint multi-stream demapping could be an alternative to conventional SIC [27]. This, of course, comes at the cost of higher computational complexity. Another class of detectors are iterative detectors which are based on algorithms such as belief propagation, approximate message passing, and others. There are quite a few DL approaches [28], [29], [30] that unfold the iterations to multiple layers of neural network which offer better performance at reduced computational cost. The learning process of all the above machine learning schemes can be accelerated when the initial weights of the neural networks are favorable. One of the machine learning frameworks involves the use of transfer learning approaches [31], [32] that use the weights of a previously trained model. This results in reduced training samples and guarantees faster convergence of a new neural network to the updated system settings. This paper studies data-driven schemes that do not need re-training as long as the system settings remain the same.

Finally, conventional receivers are often designed under the assumption of a linear behavior of the communications channel. In the presence of non-linear distortion, arising for example from non-linearities in the transceivers, such designs are no longer optimal (see e.g., analysis for maximum-likelihood receivers due to power saturation in [33]). Unless such distortion can be accurately incorporated into the model via e.g., Volterra series [34], which proves to be difficult in general, their performance tends to collapse even for moderate distortion levels. Regarding the use of neural network based receivers for non-linear end-to-end communication channels, the authors in [35] study the potential of data-driven schemes for MIMO communications scenarios. However, their design also requires model re-training for each channel realization.

A. CONTRIBUTIONS

This paper investigates how RSMA, which has been shown to outperform traditional OMA/NOMA schemes in terms of system capacity, multiplexing gain, and spectral efficiency [1], [2], [11], can benefit from the use of deep learning. Specifically, we propose the combined use of deep learning architectures for channel estimation and symbol detection in such a way that the RSMA receiver does not need to be retrained at each new channel realization. This approach, which leverages our previous work in [36], is in stark contrast with a vast majority of approaches from the literature

such as [19], [20], [21], [22], and [23]. To achieve this, we explore the use of deep learning detection architectures that incorporate the channel state information as an input. More specifically, we begin by considering a sequential detection mechanism of the common and private symbol streams using neural networks (RS-Net). This is similar to the conventional SIC receiver, but neural networks are used to replace the signal processing blocks. The performance of RS-Net architecture has certain limitations, thus we propose RS-Net+ which is an advanced version that outperforms SIC receivers.

Unlike [21], in our scheme the steps of SIC and symbol detection of the private stream are performed by a *single* NN (as shown in Section III-B ahead), this allowing to reduce its computational complexity. Going one step beyond, we refine the detector of the common stream by incorporating an additional input: soft-information of the private message of the user, leading to the advanced architecture referred to as RS-Net+. This soft-information of the private message is computed from the received signal and channel state information. This add-on will be shown to significantly improve the performance of the receiver, at a moderate increase of its computational complexity. Our schemes go beyond the work in [28] and [30] in that (i) we consider RSMA-MIMO settings (vs. plain MIMO scenarios in the above references); and (ii) channel estimation is performed by neural networks (vs. using linear/conventional schemes or, simply, assuming the channel to be known).

The contributions are summarized as following:

- The combined use of neural network-based channel estimation and symbol detection blocks leads to the architecture of RS-Net (SIC based). Although the neural networks in RS-Net replace the signal processing blocks in a conventional SIC, this paper is the first attempt to evaluate such data-driven schemes which do not need retraining for each channel realization.
- The main novelty of our work is the RS-Net+ architecture which proposes to incorporate soft-information related to private message of the said user.
- We explore a joint detection (non-SIC) scheme inspired by [27], but based on neural networks (Joint-Net). Specifically, it performs a simultaneous detection of the two underlying symbol streams (common and private) that are intended to a specific user.
- We use 1D-CNN architecture to perform channel estimation in RS-Net and Joint-Net schemes. It was shown in our previous work [24] to outperform other DNN and 2D-CNN architectures in terms of performance and computational complexity. We extend the analysis to cover channel estimation under RSMA settings.

The performance of these different architectures is evaluated by analyzing the trade-off between symbol error rate and computational complexity under different degrees of channel impairments and imperfections in both CSIT (imperfections in precoding) and CSIR (non-linearity at receivers). Specifically, for the latter we introduce power clipping in the

amplifiers. This results in a non-linear end-to-end communications system which severely affects the performance of conventional schemes. Conversely, the proposed data-driven schemes are able to incorporate such a mismatch in the resulting models and therefore incorporate robustness against this type of system imperfection.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section II describes the downlink MIMO-RSMA system model and the proposed design of the precoding matrix at the transmitter, together with an overview of a number of benchmarking detection schemes considered in this work. Section III introduces the proposed NN-enhanced RSMA receiver (RS-Net), giving special emphasis to the implementation of the channel estimation and symbol detection blocks using DNNs. Section IV studies the advanced receiver architecture that incorporates additional soft-information, namely RS-Net+. Finally, Section V introduces the Joint-Net architecture for joint multi-stream detection, which can only be used in *multi*-antenna receivers. The numerical simulation study is presented in Section VI, computational complexity analysis in Section VII, and conclusions are finally drawn in Section VIII.

II. SIGNAL AND SYSTEM MODEL

Consider the downlink of a multi-user MIMO system where one Base Station (BS) equipped with N_T transmit antennas serves K users with N_R antennas each. In 1-layer RS, the message W_k intended for the k -th user is split at the transmitter into two sub-messages namely, sub-message $W_{c,k}$ and one private sub-message $W_{p,k}$. The sub-messages of all users $W_{c,1}, \dots, W_{c,K}$ are combined into one common message W_c and encoded into a common stream s_c using a codebook shared by all users. The entire common message W_c has to be decoded by all users, yet only the corresponding sub-message $W_{c,k}$ is of interest to the k -th user. The private sub-messages of all users $W_{p,1}, \dots, W_{p,K}$ are independently encoded into private streams s_1, \dots, s_K , which are decoded by the corresponding users only.¹ Therefore, in total $K + 1$ streams, i.e. $\mathbf{s} = [s_c, s_1, \dots, s_K]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{(K+1) \times 1}$ are created from the K messages W_1, \dots, W_K . Figure 1 illustrates a typical scenario of such MIMO 1-layer RSMA system.

The streams are linearly transformed via multiplication with the precoding matrix $\mathbf{P} = [\mathbf{p}_c, \mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{p}_K]$ where $\mathbf{p}_c, \mathbf{p}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_T \times 1}, k = 1, \dots, K$ are the unit-norm beamforming vectors (to be designed, see next subsection). The transmit signal thus reads

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{P}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{s} = \alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c s_c + \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k s_k \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{A} is a diagonal matrix containing the values $\alpha_c, \alpha_k \in [0, 1]$ for $k = 1, \dots, K$, which are the coefficients that control the amount of power that is allocated to the common and private streams. These coefficients are assumed

¹See [1] and [2] for an in-depth description of RSMA.

FIGURE 1. A 1-layer RS model with K users. The common stream W_c is intended for all users, whereas private streams are individual to each user.

to be normalized, such that $\alpha_c^2 + \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k^2 = 1$. The received signal at k -th user is thus given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y}_k &= \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{P}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{s} + \mathbf{n}_k \\ &= \mathbf{H}_k \alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c s_c + \mathbf{H}_k \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k s_k + \sum_{j \neq k} \mathbf{H}_k \alpha_j \mathbf{p}_j s_j + \mathbf{n}_k \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_T}$ is the channel matrix of the k -th user, which is Gaussian distributed; \mathbf{n}_k denotes i.i.d. Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) with zero mean and variance σ^2 . At the receiver, each user first decodes the common stream s_c into W_c by treating the interference from all private streams as noise. Using Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC), W_c is then re-encoded, precoded, and subtracted from the received signal such that user- k decodes its private stream s_k into $W_{p,k}$ by treating the remaining interference from the other private streams as noise. Finally, the k -th user reconstructs the original message by extracting $W_{c,k}$ from W_c , and combining $W_{c,k}$ with $W_{p,k}$ into W_k .

A. DESIGN OF THE PRECODING MATRIX

The precoding design outlined in this section is for an underloaded scenario where $N_T \geq KN_R$. With respect to the precoding matrix \mathbf{P} , the first column of this matrix corresponds to the precoder of the common stream \mathbf{p}_c , which must be built such that the message can be effectively received by all the users in the system. To achieve this, we select \mathbf{p}_c as the principal eigenvector (i.e., eigenvector associated to the largest eigenvalue) of the matrix $\sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{H}_k^H \mathbf{H}_k$. This guarantees that the transmitted power is maximized towards all the directions where users are present, without per-user priorities. Regarding the precoder vectors associated to the private streams, we build them so that they are completely orthogonal to one another, similar to the approach in [37]. This is carried out while maximizing the received power

towards the user of interest. To formulate this, consider the following $(K - 1)N_R \times N_T$ channel matrix

$$\mathbf{H}_{(k)} = [\mathbf{H}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{H}_{k-1}^T, \mathbf{H}_{k+1}^T, \dots, \mathbf{H}_K^T]^T$$

which is formed by stacking the channel matrices of all users *except for the k -th user* on top of one another. Let \mathbf{Q}_k denote the unique $N_T \times N_T - (K - 1)N_R$ matrix of orthogonal columns such that

$$\mathbf{H}_{(k)}\mathbf{Q}_k = \mathbf{0}.$$

In other words, the columns of \mathbf{Q}_k span the orthogonal complement (of rank $N_T - (K - 1)N_R$) to the subspace spanned by the rows of $\mathbf{H}_{(k)}$. It should be noted that this guarantees $\mathbf{H}_j\mathbf{Q}_k = \mathbf{0}$ for all $j \neq k$. The k -th precoding vector \mathbf{p}_k is therefore built as $\mathbf{p}_k = \mathbf{Q}_k\mathbf{w}_k$, where \mathbf{w}_k is the principal eigenvector of the matrix $\mathbf{Q}_k^H\mathbf{H}_k^H\mathbf{H}_k\mathbf{Q}_k$.

In this work, we also consider the case of imperfect precoders resulting from the use of noisy CSIT, that is, noisy channel estimates $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_k$ (instead of \mathbf{H}_k) in the preceding expressions. To model this, we let

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}_k = \mathbf{H}_k + \mathbf{N}_k \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{N}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_T}$ represents the zero-mean AWGN of variance β^2 . With imperfect precoders, the orthogonality of the private streams is not preserved. In the computer simulation results, we analyze how this impacts the performance of NN-based and conventional receivers.

B. CONVENTIONAL DETECTION OF RSMA SIGNALS

Throughout this work, we adopt as benchmarks (i) the Maximum Likelihood (ML) detector, which is optimal yet computationally intensive; and (ii) two sub-optimal schemes: the Linear Minimum Mean Square Error (LMMSE) and Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC) detectors. All of them are succinctly described next.

- **ML detection:** Here, a minimum distance estimation rule is applied to all the common and private message pairs (i.e., W_c, W_j for all j), namely,

$$\underset{W_c, W_1, \dots, W_K}{\operatorname{argmin}} \quad \|\mathbf{y}_k - \mathbf{H}_k\alpha_c\mathbf{p}_c\phi_c(W_c) - \sum_j \mathbf{H}_k\alpha_j\mathbf{p}_j\phi_j(W_j)\|^2$$

where $\phi_c(\cdot), \phi_j(\cdot)$ represent the encoding and modulating functionality of the common and private messages of j -th user. We assume that the ML detector has complete knowledge of the channel matrix of each user \mathbf{H}_k .

- **LMMSE detection:** Alternatively, when the receiver is equipped with multiple antennas, a conventional LMMSE receiver can be used to (i) *jointly* estimate the common and private message of the intended user; and (ii) mitigate the interference caused by the other private messages (owing to the additional spatial dimension). In this case, assuming that the transmitted symbols are zero-mean with unit power, the estimates read

$$[\hat{s}_c^{(\text{LMMSE})}, \hat{s}_k^{(\text{LMMSE})}]^T = \mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})H} \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \mathbf{y}_k$$

where $\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})}$ is the $N_R \times 2$ *equivalent* channel given by the product of the *known* channel matrix and the precoding vectors for the common and private messages, namely,

$$\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})} = \mathbf{H}_k[\alpha_c\mathbf{p}_c, \alpha_k\mathbf{p}_k] \quad (4)$$

and \mathbf{C}_k is the covariance matrix at the k -th user

$$\mathbf{C}_k = \alpha_c^2 \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{p}_c \mathbf{p}_c^H \mathbf{H}_k^H + \sum_{j=1}^K \alpha_j^2 \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{p}_j \mathbf{p}_j^H \mathbf{H}_k^H + \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_R}.$$

- **SIC detection:** SIC turns out to be a simpler alternative. First, it obtains an LMMSE estimate of common symbol:

$$\hat{s}_c^{(\text{SIC})} = \alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c^H \mathbf{H}_k^H \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \mathbf{y}_k$$

After performing a hard decision on $\hat{s}_c^{(\text{SIC})}$ and subtracting (from the received signal) the regenerated input signal corresponding to the common part, an estimate of the private symbol can be obtained by using the LMMSE receiver on the clean signal $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_k$:

$$\hat{s}_k^{(\text{SIC})} = \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k^H \mathbf{H}_k^H \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_k^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_k.$$

where the corresponding covariance matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_k$ now reads

$$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_k = \sum_{j=1}^K \alpha_j^2 \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{p}_j \mathbf{p}_j^H \mathbf{H}_k^H + \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_R}.$$

III. RS-NET: AN NN-BASED RSMA RECEIVER

In this section, we leverage the traditional SIC architecture for the receiver and replace (i) the conventional channel estimation block; (ii) data detection block for the common stream; and (iii) the signal re-construction, precoding and subtraction blocks needed to detect the private stream by their NN counterparts. The resulting scheme is depicted in Figure 2. In the sequel, it will be referred to as RS-Net receiver.

FIGURE 2. RS-Net receiver architecture for decoding the common (s_c) and private (s_k) streams of user- k .

A. CHANNEL ESTIMATION VIA 1D-CNN

For channel estimation, the received signal corresponding to the transmission of N_P pilot symbols can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{Y}_P = \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{X}_P + \mathbf{N}_k \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{Y}_P \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_P}$, $\mathbf{H}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_T}$ is the k -th user's channel matrix and $\mathbf{X}_P = [\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{N_P}] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_T \times N_P}$ denotes the unit modulus transmit QPSK signals; $\mathbf{N} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_P}$ represents the zero-mean i.i.d. additive Gaussian white noise of variance σ^2 .

Throughout this paper, for LMMSE and SIC detection, the channel is estimated via Least Squares (LS) estimation. This method is used for all linear and non-linear scenarios to compare the robustness of conventional and data-driven schemes. The user channel is computed using the transmitted pilots \mathbf{X}_P and received signals \mathbf{Y}_P as follows

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}}_k^{\text{LS}} = \mathbf{Y}_P \mathbf{X}_P^H (\mathbf{X}_P \mathbf{X}_P^H)^{-1} \quad (6)$$

The task of channel estimation can be modeled as a supervised learning *regression* problem. In our previous work [24], we found that *shallow* 1D-CNNs (Convolutional Neural Networks) exhibit an optimal performance-complexity trade-off. Consequently, we cast channel estimation into a multi-output regression task where:

- The input of the 1D-CNN (see Figure 3) is given by $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}} = \text{vec}[\text{Re}(\mathbf{Y}_k) \otimes [1, 0] + \text{Im}(\mathbf{Y}_k) \otimes [0, 1]]$ where $\mathbf{Y}_k = [\mathbf{y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{y}_{N_P}] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_P}$ are the received signals of user- k on transmitting N_P pilot symbols. The vector is then reshaped to size $N_R \times 2N_P$
- The output is the effective channel vector $\text{vec}[\text{Re}(\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})}) \otimes [1, 0] + \text{Im}(\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})}) \otimes [0, 1]]$ where $\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})} = \mathbf{H}_k [\alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c, \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k]$ is the effective channel matrix defined in (4).

FIGURE 3. 1D-CNN for channel estimation.

In 1D-CNNs, the trainable weights are arranged in 2D kernels for convolution operations. However, these kernels slide in *one* direction only (e.g., along the time axis) to produce feature maps. As shown in Figure 3, there are as many feature maps as the number of kernels N_k in the convolutional layer. The feature maps are then flattened and connected to the output layer. This 1D-CNN is said to be shallow since it comprises one *single* convolutional layer.

Each of the kernels ($1 \dots N_k$) is denoted by $\mathbf{K}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{k_h \times k_w}$, where k_h and k_w stand for the kernel height and width,

respectively. The kernel convolves on the input (or previous feature map, in the general case) $\mathbf{Y}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{h_l \times w_l}$, where h_l and w_l denote its height and width. The generated output feature map $\mathbf{Z}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times (w_l - k_w + 1)}$ can thus be expressed as

$$(\mathbf{Z}_l)_n = \sum_{i=1}^{k_h} \sum_{j=1}^{k_w} (\mathbf{K}_l)_{i,j} (\mathbf{Y}_l)_{i,j+n-1} \quad (7)$$

The training of a CNN model [38] involves identifying the kernel weights that are optimized for the regression task.

B. SYMBOL DETECTION VIA DNN

Data (symbol) detection can be modeled as a supervised learning classification problem which can be efficiently solved via feed-forward DNNs. In particular, it can be cast into a multi-class classification task where:

- The input of the DNN for the detection of the *common* message symbol, as depicted in Figure 2, is given by (i) the received signal \mathbf{y}_k ; and (ii) the estimated (or actual) equivalent channel matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_k^{(\text{eq})}$ re-shaped into a row vector $\mathbf{t} = \text{vec}([\mathbf{y}_k, \hat{\mathbf{H}}_k^{(\text{eq})}])$. In addition to these inputs, the DNN for the detection of the *private* symbols also takes in the estimated common symbol obtained by the previous neural network. The *Map* block transforms the discrete output (an index, see next bullet) of the NN in a modulated symbol suitable for transmission.
- The output is an index b to the set of transmitted symbols of cardinality B . In other words, for each message stream (common/private), we have $b \in [1, \dots, B]$ with $B = 2^S$, where S denotes the number of bits per symbol.

FIGURE 4. The multi-layer perceptron, a feedforward DNN for symbol detection.

Feed-forward DNN architectures include Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) which is depicted in Figure 4. The L -layer MLP consists of: (i) one input layer with $2N_R$ elements (the real and imaginary parts of the received signal) plus the $2 \cdot N_R$ coefficients of the effective common channel $\mathbf{H}_k^{(\text{eq})}$; (ii) one output layer with B neurons; and (iii) $L - 2$ hidden layers with N_l ; $l = 2, \dots, L - 1$ neurons each.

This MLP defines a mapping $f(t, \Phi) : \mathbb{R}^{2N_R(1+N_T)} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^B$ of an input vector t onto an output vector \mathbf{r}_L through L

iterative processing steps

$$r_l = f_l(r_{l-1}; \phi_l); \quad l = 1 \dots L \quad (8)$$

where $f_l(r_{l-1}, \phi_l) : \mathbb{R}^{N_{l-1}} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{N_l}$ is the mapping associated to the l -th layer. This mapping depends on the output from the previous layer and on the parameter set of the said layer, ϕ_l , with $\Phi = [\phi_1, \dots, \phi_L]$ denoting the set of all parameters in the model. The l -th layer is said to be *dense* if $f_l(r_{l-1}; \phi_l)$ is of the form

$$f_l(r_{l-1}; \phi_l) = \sigma(\mathbf{G}_l r_{l-1} + \mathbf{u}_l) \quad (9)$$

with $\mathbf{G}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{N_l \times N_{l-1}}$ and $\mathbf{u}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{N_l}$ denoting matrix of weights and bias vector, while $\sigma(\cdot)$ being a (typically non-linear) activation function. In this work, Rectified Linear Units (ReLU) are used as activation functions in all hidden layers. The output layer has the Softmax activation function, to compute the probability for *each* set of transmit symbols. Further, each dense layer is followed by a batch normalization and dropout layer which is typically used to avoid overfitting to the training dataset.

In the training phase, the parameter set in each layer, i.e., $\phi_l = [\mathbf{G}_l, \mathbf{u}_l]$, is adjusted via the stochastic adaptive gradient descent algorithm (Adagrad, [39]) and back-propagation [40]. The goal is to minimize the categorical cross entropy, thereby maximizing classification accuracy (i.e., minimize SER).

C. RS-NET: CONSIDERATIONS ON TRAINING

RS-Net does not require re-training of the neural networks for each channel realization or on a frame-by-frame basis. The various neural networks are trained offline and can be used for channel estimation or symbol detection as long as the system scenario i.e., number of transmit antennas, users, and channel statistics remains unchanged.

The training dataset for *channel estimation* comprises a total of M examples of received signals $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}^{(m)}$, $m = 1, \dots, M$ as input features, and the corresponding equivalent (vector) channel as labels, as per the definition in Section III-A. For the symbol detection blocks, the input features are the received signal and the equivalent channel, whereas the output is the corresponding common (or private) symbol. The generation of the training dataset comprises of the following steps:

- 1) Generation of the received signal for a total of M realizations of the communication scenario. For each realization of the channel, N_P pilot symbols and noise vectors are generated, followed by N_D data symbols.
- 2) Letting the label of each pilot symbol block be the actual effective channel response, for the channel estimation block. For symbol detection, on the contrary, the labels are given by the corresponding common and private symbols for each sample.

IV. RS-NET+: AN ENHANCED RS-NET ARCHITECTURE

For scenarios with *multi*-antenna users, we propose an enhanced architecture that takes advantage of the additional

FIGURE 5. Proposed RS-Net+ receiver architecture for decoding the common (s_c) and private (s_k) streams of user- k .

spatial degrees of freedom. As shown in Figure 5, the common stream detection block is provided with two additional input features to the first layer: the private channel coefficients in $\mathbf{H}_k^{(eq)}$ along with a soft estimate of the *intended* private message symbol ($\hat{s}_{p\text{-soft}}$). The intuition behind providing a soft estimate of the private message symbol *and* the corresponding estimate of the private channel (which is part of $\mathbf{H}_k^{(eq)}$) is to improve the detection of the common stream by letting the NN to implicitly reconstruct and subtract the contribution of the private message to the received signal. As we will see in the Computer Simulation Results (Section VI), this is possible even for soft estimates of low quality.

The soft estimate of the private symbol can be independently computed from the received signal and effective channel matrix of the k -th user as:

$$\hat{s}_{p\text{-soft},k} = \frac{(\mathbf{H}_k \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k)^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp \mathbf{y}_k}{\sigma^2 + (\mathbf{H}_k \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k)^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp \mathbf{h}_k \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k} \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{P}_c^\perp is the orthogonal projection matrix (which is only defined for $N_R > 1$) onto the null space of the equivalent common message channel vector $\mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{p}_c$, that is

$$\mathbf{P}_c^\perp = \mathbf{I}_{N_R} - \frac{\mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{p}_c \mathbf{P}_c^H \mathbf{H}_k^H}{\mathbf{P}_c^H \mathbf{H}_k^H \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{p}_c}$$

The above soft estimate can be seen as an LMMSE estimator of the private intended symbol when the common symbol is estimated according to the maximum-likelihood principle. The complete derivation is attached as Appendix I.

V. JOINT-NET: JOINT DETECTION OF RSMA SIGNALS

In the RS-Net and RS-Net+ approaches, the common and private streams are *sequentially* processed via SIC operation. Here, we propose to *jointly* detect both messages with a single neural network. This is only possible in scenarios with multi-antenna terminals owing to the additional spatial degrees of freedom provided by MIMO architectures.

The proposed Joint-Net receiver architecture is depicted in Figure 6. Instead of two symbol detection blocks (for the

FIGURE 6. Proposed Joint-Net receiver architecture for parallel detection of the common (s_c) and private (s_k) streams of user- k .

common and private streams), here a *single* detection block takes in as input the received signal (\mathbf{y}_k) and the estimated channel ($\mathbf{H}_k^{(eq)}$). At the output, the estimates for the common and private symbols (s_c and s_k) of the k -th user are obtained. To produce those estimates, we leverage again on a feed-forward DNN. However, to avoid the curse of dimensionality (i.e., exponential growth of complexity associated to the joint detection of multiple signals), we transform the *multi-class* classification problem into a *multi-label* classification task. In other words, rather than producing a single one-hot encoding vector at output of the neural network for both the common and private symbols, now we have two one-hot encoding vectors, one for each symbol. For example, for QPSK signals the output layer of Joint-Net has eight neurons, four each to represent the corresponding one-hot encoding vector of the set of transmitted common and private QPSK symbols.

The major difference between the neural networks in the symbol detection blocks of the Joint-Net vs. RS-Net architectures is at the output layer. In Joint-Net, it employs a *sigmoid* activation function to predict the probabilities of the symbol belonging to the said classes, similar to decoding of signals from multiple antennas in a single forward pass [23]. In summary, for the Joint-Net architecture:

- The input of the DNN for the joint detection of the common and private symbol is given by (i) the received signal \mathbf{y}_k ; and (ii) the estimated equivalent channel matrix $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_k^{(eq)}$ re-shaped into a row vector $\mathbf{t} = \text{vec}([\mathbf{y}_k, \hat{\mathbf{H}}_k^{(eq)}])$.
- The output is given by two indices $b_c, b_k \in [1, \dots, B_c + B_p]$, with B_c and B_p denoting the cardinality of the corresponding symbol sets (i.e., constellation sizes) for the common and private channels.

VI. COMPUTER SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we extensively assess the performance of the proposed RS-Net, RS-Net+, Joint-Net receiver architectures in a variety of operating conditions. The scenario comprises $K=2$ *single-* or *multi-*antenna users, and one Base

Station (BS) equipped with $N_T = \{3, 6\}$ transmit antennas,² respectively. The communication system has been implemented using Sionna [41], a TensorFlow-based open-source library. For implementation, training, and performance evaluation, we use Keras [42] on a TensorFlow backend [43]. A different instance (model) of the NN is fit for each SNR in the range of interest to ensure optimal performance. To that aim, the learning rate of the stochastic adaptive gradient descent algorithm (Adagrad) is set to 0.01, and a batch size of 512 samples is used for gradient computations. The hyper-parameters (e.g., number of layers, neurons per layer) are optimized via grid search. Out of the $M = 10^4$ examples in the generated dataset, 20% are used for validation. Unless otherwise stated, the neural networks are trained for 50 epochs which ensures convergence.

We start by investigating the optimum power allocation among the common and private streams. Then, we assess the performance of the (NN-based) channel estimation block which is used in the RS-Net, RS-Net+, Joint-Net receiver architectures proposed in this work. Next, we carry out an in-depth analysis of the symbol error rate performance (i.e., symbol detection) of the proposed architectures. The analysis includes impact of imperfect precoding at the BS in the proposed schemes which compromises the orthogonality among the private streams intended for each user. This can be potentially harmful for the SIC-based schemes due to error propagation effects. Finally, we thoroughly investigate the impact of power clipping in the amplifiers. This is aimed to illustrate the robustness of the proposed NN-based receiver architectures to *non-linearities* in the (end-to-end) communications channel. Notice that such effects cannot be accounted for by the benchmark schemes which are based on *linear* processing.

A. OPTIMAL POWER ALLOCATION

As explained in Section II, the power allocation coefficients (α_c, α_k) of the common and private streams are governed by $\alpha_c^2 + \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k^2 = 1$. Given the symmetry of the scenario, we restrict ourselves to the case of identical power allocation to all private streams (i.e., $\alpha_k = \alpha$ for all k). Specifically, we calculate the Symbol Error Rate (SER) of the optimum Maximum-Likelihood (ML) detector introduced in Section II-B. The optimal α_c and α_k values are averaged for a number of channel realizations. For simplicity, we adopt the power allocation values of the optimum ML detector in all the proposed NN-based receivers, as well as the conventional ones (LMMSE, SIC) which are used as benchmarks.

In Figure 7, we depict the *total* SER by counting the number of errors both in the common and private streams. Interestingly, the SER curves are relatively flat for a broad range ($\alpha_k \in [0.2, 0.65]$) of power allocation values. This observation is similar for all the SNRs under consideration. In Figure 8, we look at the individual plots of SER of the

²The proposed schemes can be generalized to a higher number of users as long as the number of transmit antennas is adjusted accordingly.

common and private streams. In the left sub-plot (Common Message SER), very high levels of power allocation to private streams means less power to common stream, thus records high SER for high α . In the right sub-plot (Private Message SER), at very low power allocation values to private streams, detection of private stream suffers because the majority of power is allocated to the common stream. The effect of power allocation is more pronounced in a SIC receiver. The errors in detection of common stream (due to low power allocation to common precoder) propagate into private stream detection as well (due to invalid SIC), thus affecting the total SER. Hence, to minimize the total error count, the power allocation to private streams must be in the mid-region to avoid extreme cases that lead to poor private SER.

Results are given for a scenario with single-antenna users ($N_R = 1$) for QPSK modulation, similar results were obtained in the multi-antenna users. Consequently, hereinafter we let $\alpha_k = 0.3$ for all scenarios.

FIGURE 7. Total symbol error rate of the ML detector as a function of the power allocation to the private streams ($N_T = 3$, $N_R = 1$, $K = 2$).

FIGURE 8. Symbol error rate (Common and Private Stream) of the ML detector as a function of the power allocation to the private streams ($N_T = 3$, $N_R = 1$, $K = 2$).

B. CHANNEL ESTIMATION PERFORMANCE

The estimation error is given by the squared norm of the difference between the equivalent $N_R \times 2$ channel matrix $\mathbf{H}_k^{(eq)} = \mathbf{H}_k[\alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c, \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k]$ and its estimate. The squared error matrix is normalized column-wise, i.e., with respect to $\|\mathbf{H}_k \alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c\|^2$ and $\|\mathbf{H}_k \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k\|^2$, respectively. In other words, the estimation error is given in terms of normalized mean-squared error (NMSE). For the estimation of the equivalent channel matrix $\mathbf{H}_k^{(eq)}$, we use $N_P = 3$ pilot symbols which is the bare minimum required to estimate the three channel coefficients which are associated to the common and two private streams in a

two-user scenario. As a benchmark, we adopt a linear Least Squares (LS) channel estimator which is optimal for Gaussian channels and high SNR. However, the equivalent channel is given by the product of precoding vector and channel matrix, which results in a non-Gaussian distribution. This motivates the use of non-linear channel estimators such as 1D-CNNs.

Figure 9 (left) depicts the Normalized Mean Square Error (NMSE) as a function of the SNR for the common and private channels of user 1 (user 2 yields similar results since the scenario is symmetric). Clearly, the NMSE is higher in the private channels than in the common channel. This is attributed to the fact that private channels are allocated a small fraction of the transmit power ($\alpha_k = 0.3$). The figure also reveals that 1D-CNN estimators consistently outperform their LS counterparts (which are not optimal, as discussed above) in all scenarios, and across all SNRs for both channels. Such gain leverages on two effects: the non-linear processing in 1D-CNN; and the exploitation of the channel statistics knowledge learnt by neural network during training stage. It is to be noted that as the effective channel is not Gaussian, the optimum estimator does not need to be linear. As expected, in the low-SNR regime where the performance of the LS estimator is necessarily worse, the gap is slightly larger. This holds in particular for the power-constrained private stream. As a final remark, the performance gain associated to the 1D-CNN estimator is admittedly moderate in linear channel scenarios. However, the situation becomes radically different for non-linear channels (see Section VI-D ahead).

We also study the degradation associated to the use of imperfect precoders resulting from the use of noisy CSIT, as discussed in Section II-A. Figure 9 (right) reveals that for moderate values of imperfect precoders ($\beta^2 = 0.1$), the degradation is marginal. For the LS estimator, this is due to the fact that inter-user interference is accurately modeled in (2) and all system parameters in the third summation (α_k, s_k) are known except for the additive noise, which is only statistically characterized. This allows the LS scheme to effectively estimate $\mathbf{H}_k^{(eq)}$ irrespective of the equivalent channel (which also depends on the value of β^2). Interestingly, the same behavior is observed for the 1D-CNN estimator.

To conclude this subsection, we investigate the impact of the training dataset size on the NMSE performance. Figure 10 shows that the NMSE of the 1D-CNN estimator reaches a floor for datasets of more than 10,000 examples.³ This observation is in line with the results in [24] which highlights one of the main reasons for using 1D-CNN: in MIMO-RSMA scenarios, the application of DNN channel estimator would require a deeper architecture (i.e., higher computational complexity) and a larger training dataset to reach convergence. Unsurprisingly, the estimate for the common channel exhibits a better performance than that of the private channel, owing to the relatively higher power allocation.

³In this case, the neural network is trained for a total of 100 epochs to ensure convergence across all sizes of the training dataset.

FIGURE 9. Channel estimation error for the 1D-CNN and LS channel estimators in a scenario with multi-antenna users and perfect or imperfect precoders ($N_T = 6$, $N_R = 2$, $N_k = 64$ kernels of size $N_R \times 2$).

FIGURE 10. Channel estimation performance vs. size of the training dataset size (SNR = 20 dB, 100 training epochs, $N_k = 64$ kernels of size $N_R \times 2$).

C. SYMBOL DETECTION PERFORMANCE

In this section, we evaluate the SER performance of the proposed RS-Net, RS-Net+ and Joint-Net architectures with linear channels. The benchmarks are those introduced in Section II-B, namely: the ML, LMMSE (for multi-antenna users only), and SIC detectors. For the sake of a fair comparison, each detector operates with different CSIR. Specifically, the RS-Net, RS-Net+ (again, for multi-antenna users only), and Joint-Net detectors take advantage of the NN-based channel estimates which are obtained via 1D-CNNs. On the contrary, the conventional LMMSE and SIC detectors use the conventional channel estimates provided by the LS channel estimator. In this way, they illustrate the performance achievable by state-of-the-art channel estimators and detectors. Finally, the ML detector operates with full CSI for the channel response and the actual (im)perfect precoders used in each scenario. Hence, the ML detector will attain the lowest possible SER.

First, our analysis focuses on an RSMA system with QPSK modulation in both the common and private streams. After grid-search optimization, the optimal performance for the

RS-Net is attained for DNNs with two hidden layers with $N_l = 128$ neurons each, followed by a batch normalization and a dropout layer with probability 0.3 (same configuration in the detection blocks for the common and private streams). For RS-Net+, the optimal performance was achieved with 2 hidden layers of 32 and 64 neurons, respectively. Joint-Net operates with two dense layers with $N_l = 256$ neurons in each, also followed by batch normalization and dropout layers. The training dataset comprises $M = 10^4$ examples, and in each example the payload includes $N_D = 10$ randomly-generated data symbols. A detailed view of the hyperparameters for RS-Net+ and Joint-Net is provided in Table 1 for the two modulation schemes studied.

FIGURE 11. Symbol error rate in the common and private streams for single ($N_R = 1$, $N_T = 3$) and multi-antenna ($N_R = 2$, $N_T = 6$) users and QPSK modulation. Solid lines are for perfect ($\beta^2 = 0$) precoding, and dashed lines for imperfect precoding ($\beta^2 = 0.2$).

Figure 11 depicts the SER for both the common and private streams. As expected, the curve for the ML detector acts as a lower bound for the SER performance in all cases. The curve for the LMMSE detector⁴ is a valid upper bound in the multi-antenna case only. Further, by comparing the top and bottom sub-plots, one observes that using multiple antennas substantially improves the achievable SER performance.

⁴Note that the LMMSE and SIC curves completely overlap for the common channel since, by construction, the SIC and LMMSE detector are identical for the common channel.

TABLE 1. Hyperparameters for different neural network schemes ($N_T = 6$, $N_R = 2$, $K = 2$).

	RS-Net+		Joint-Net	
	QPSK	16QAM	QPSK	16QAM
Number of hidden layers	2	2	2	4
Number of neurons	[32, 64]	[64, 256]	[256] x 2	[512] x 4
Training dataset size	10^4	10^5	10^4	10^5
Number of epochs	50	50	50	100
Output Activation	Softmax		Sigmoid	
Loss Function	Categorical Cross-entropy		Binary Cross-entropy	
Task	Multi-class Classification		Multi-label Classification	

In both single- and multi-antenna settings, RS-Net substantially outperforms the conventional SIC receiver in the low SNR regime. However, for large SNR values (above 30-35 dB and 20 dB, respectively), the RS-Net curves exhibit an error floor. Interestingly, such error floor vanishes and performance substantially improves when the soft estimate of the user's private symbol given by (20) is used as an additional input in the RS-Net+ scheme. This indicates that the intended private stream causes significant interference in the decoding of *common* message and especially at high SNR, which results in the above-mentioned error floor of the RS-Net scheme. On the contrary, intra-user interference is effectively removed by the RS-Net+ scheme even if the soft estimate happens to be a coarse one (i.e., relatively poor SER). To illustrate this, the SER associated to the soft estimate of private symbol is depicted in Figure 11 (bottom-right).

We also observe that Joint-Net clearly outperforms the RS-Net and RS-Net+ schemes, this highlighting the penalty associated to error propagation in the SIC operation, and thus the gap with the optimal ML detector is narrower. However, this comes at the expense of a deeper architecture and hence higher computational complexity (see next section). As for the private stream, it suffers from the error floor exhibited by the RS-Net when detecting the *common* stream symbols. In the case of imperfect precoders ($\beta = 0.2$), all the receivers exhibit some performance degradation due to inter-user interference, with RS-Net+ and Joint-Net consistently offering better performance than the conventional LMMSE and SIC receivers. Interestingly, SIC is particularly sensitive to precoder imperfections: due to error propagation, the SER performance of the private stream detector collapses and becomes even worse than that of the LMMSE scheme. On the contrary, the degradation exhibited by deep-learning schemes is moderate, as discussed above. For higher values of β^2 , this effect is even more noticeable.

Complementarily, we want to assess the penalty coming from the use of estimated CSIR, that is, $\hat{\mathbf{H}}_k^{(eq)}$ instead of known (or ideal) CSIR $\mathbf{H}_k^{(eq)}$, in all the detection schemes.⁵ The goal is to isolate the effects and analyze the impact of 1D-CNN based channel estimation on the performance of symbol detection, i.e., error propagation due to poor channel

⁵Here, we focus on the perfect precoding case (i.e., $\beta^2 = 0$), for brevity.

FIGURE 12. Symbol error rate in the common stream with known (solid) and estimated (dashed) channel state information obtained with the corresponding channel estimation scheme ($N_R = 2$, $N_T = 6$, $\beta^2 = 0$).

estimation. This is accomplished in Figure 12. Clearly, the Joint-Net scheme exhibits the widest gap, this revealing that it is highly sensitive to channel estimation errors. This happens even if the quality of the CSI estimates obtained by the 1D-CNN estimator is quite high, as reported in Figure 9. The penalty for the SIC scheme (which uses an LS channel estimator) is moderate, while the penalty is marginal for the proposed RS-Net+ detection scheme. The errors in the detection of the common stream carry over to the detection of the private stream, but they are not shown here for brevity.

To close this section, we are interested in evaluating the performance of data-driven receivers with higher-order modulations. The reason is two-fold: (i) to investigate the impact of a more complex amplitude *and* phase modulation (vs. phase-only in QPSK) on SER performance; and (ii) investigate the associated performance/complexity trade-offs with larger constellations (note that e.g., the computational complexity of ML detection increases exponentially in the constellation size, as discussed in Section VII ahead). Specifically, we consider the case of using 16 QAM for data symbol transmission and QPSK-modulated pilot symbols for

increased robustness in channel estimation. Here, RS-Net and RS-Net+ require slightly higher number of neurons per layer (512 and [64, 256], respectively) when compared to those of QPSK symbol detection. In contrast, the number of layers and neurons per layer needed by the Joint-Net detection scheme *doubles* with respect to the QPSK case: 4 and 512, respectively. This unavoidably translates into a substantial increase of its computational complexity. For higher order modulation schemes, this effect becomes even more noticeable (results are omitted here for brevity). To circumvent the high computational complexity involved, resorting to more computationally efficient architectures such as Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) is recommended.

The SER results are shown in Figure 13. Now, the gain of the RS-Net+ scheme with respect to SIC detection is, admittedly, more moderate. Again, the proposed RS-Net exhibits an error floor and, further, its performance substantially degrades with respect to QPSK. Still, the degradation exhibited by Joint-Net is much higher. This indicates that the problem of detecting 16QAM symbols is too complex for an exclusively data-driven/*black box* approach such as Joint-Net which is unable to reliably detect symbols despite using more layers and neurons. On the contrary, RS-Net+ clearly benefits from the use of conventional SIC architectures in combination with data-driven schemes (i.e., a *hybrid* approach).

FIGURE 13. Symbol error rate in the common and private streams for *multi-antenna* users and 16 QAM modulation ($N_R = 2$, $N_T = 6$, $\beta^2 = 0$).

D. SPECIAL CASE: CHANNEL ESTIMATION AND SYMBOL DETECTION WITH NON-LINEAR CHANNELS

This section is aimed to illustrate the robustness of the proposed NN-based receiver architectures to non-linearities in the end-to-end communications channel. Specifically, we introduce power clipping in the receiver amplifiers. Hence, we model the amplitude modulation-to-amplitude modulation (AM/AM) for each I/Q component as:

$$\phi_{AM-AM}(x) = \begin{cases} x & \text{for } x \leq p_{\text{sat}} \\ p_{\text{sat}} & \text{for } x > p_{\text{sat}} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

In order to select the power saturation levels at which to conduct the analysis, we look at the received signal constellation points. Figure 14 depicts the real and imaginary components of the received signal for (i) linear channels (i.e., no clipping); and (ii) non-linear ones with two saturation levels: $p_{\text{sat}} = \{\sqrt{10}, \sqrt{15}\}$. Clearly, the received 16QAM symbols are spread farther apart than in QPSK. Therefore, the impact of the saturation level depends on the actual constellation. Since we are interested in scenarios with moderate clipping, we let $p_{\text{sat}} = \{\sqrt{10}, \sqrt{15}\}$ for QPSK and 16QAM, respectively.

FIGURE 14. I/Q components of the received signal for linear and non-linear channels with different saturation levels. QPSK (top) and 16QAM (bottom).

FIGURE 15. Channel estimation performance of the 1D-CNN and LS channel estimators with QPSK pilot symbols and perfect precoding $N_R = 2$, $N_k = 1280$ kernels of size $N_R \times 2$, $\beta^2 = 0$).

First, we investigate the NMSE performance of the 1D-CNN and LS channel estimators. Figure 15 reveals that the 1D-CNN estimator provides a very substantial gain (5)–7 dB with respect to the LS estimator for the whole range of SNRs under consideration. This is in stark contrast with the very limited gain in the case of linear channels, as shown in Figure 9. Clearly, the neural network is able to learn the non-linear features of the channel, whereas this is not possible for

the linear LS estimator. Again, the private channel estimate exhibits higher NMSE compared to the common channel one due to its lower power allocation.

FIGURE 16. Symbol error rate in the common (left) and private (right) channels, with QPSK (top) and 16QAM (bottom) data symbols ($p_{\text{sat}} = \sqrt{10}/\sqrt{15}$ for QPSK/16QAM symbols, $N_R = 2$, $N_T = 6$, $\beta^2 = 0$).

As for symbol detection, Figure 16 shows that all the proposed and benchmark schemes experience some degradation with respect to the case of linear channels (Figure 9). For QPSK (top plots), the degradation is particularly noticeable for the ML detector, both in the common and private channels, which is not the optimal anymore since the channel is not linear. Instead, the Joint-Net detector exhibits now the lowest SER for all SNRs. Also, the performance of the SIC detector is severely impaired, in particular for the private stream. To recall, SIC operates with an LS *linear* channel estimator which is unable to properly estimate the CSI. This, in turn, leads to an imperfect reconstruction and cancellation of the signal in the common channel and, ultimately, very poor SER in the private channel (Figure 16 right).

The impact of non-linearities is even more pronounced for a 16QAM modulation scheme (bottom plots). Here, the ML detector totally crashes exhibiting a SER performance which is even worse than that of linear detectors. The combined effect of non-linear channels with higher-order modulations is also very prominent for the SIC detector: the performance

in the common stream experiences a substantial degradation that, in turn, severely impacts in the error rate for the private stream, due to error propagation. This is also the case for the RS-Net detector. As for Joint-Net, its SER performance very seriously deteriorates too. As discussed in the previous section, the problem of detecting 16QAM symbols is far too complex for exclusively data-driven/*black-box* approaches. On top of that, power clipping renders the problem even more complex. Interestingly, the proposed RS-Net+ detector clearly outperforms any other detection scheme. However, its performance ultimately depends on the quality of the soft estimates for the private symbols. Since such estimates are obtained via the *linear* estimator (20), a more severe clipping would have a negative effect.

FIGURE 17. Constellation mappings learnt by RS-Net+ in the common (left) and private streams (right), and for linear (top) and non-linear channels (bottom) with QPSK symbols. Different colors are used to identify different constellation points ($p_{\text{sat}} = \sqrt{10}$, SNR= 30 dB, $N_R = 2$, $N_T = 6$, $\beta^2 = 0$).

Finally, we visualize the constellation mappings learnt by RS-Net+ in order to get some insights on its internal operation. This is accomplished by projecting the embedding in the hidden layers just before the output classification (i.e., symbol detection) layer onto a two-dimensional space via the t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE) tool [44]. For QPSK symbols (Figure 17) and linear channels, RS-Net+ is able to properly cluster the constellation points both for the common and private streams (top sub-plots). The inclusion of power clipping has a marginal effect, with just a few points getting scattered throughout the four clusters, as shown in the bottom sub-plots. For 16QAM symbols (Figure 18), the learnt mapping for the common channel is substantially different from that of a rotated 16QAM constellation and resembles that of [45], where auto-encoders were studied for the design of end-to-end communication systems. As for the impact of non-linearities, similar conclusions can be drawn. As for the private channel, the t-SNE *projection*,

FIGURE 18. Constellation mappings learnt by RS-Net+ in the common (left) and private streams (right), and for linear (top) and non-linear channels (bottom) with 16QAM symbols. Different colors are used to identify different constellation points ($\rho_{\text{sat}} = \sqrt{15}$, SNR= 30 dB, $N_R = 2$, $N_T = 6$, $\beta^2 = 0$).

which depends on a number of hyper-parameters, is not very informative. However, the RS-Net+ is able to properly detect the transmit symbols, as shown in the SER curves of the preceding figures.

E. SPECIAL CASE: OVERLOADED RSMA

In this section, we evaluate the neural-network based receivers for overloaded scenario, where the total number of receive antennas exceeds the number of transmit antennas. RSMA has been shown to be a robust interference scheme for overloaded cases [1], [7], outperforming other non-orthogonal multiple access schemes. We seek to investigate the performance of RS-Net and Joint-Net schemes against conventional LMMSE/SIC and ML receivers. We adapt the system model to a scenario where we can visualize the beamforming pattern to observe the impact of power allocation to private streams. This is followed by channel estimation, and symbol detection performance. To recap, the RSMA signal model reads as below

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y}_k &= \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{P} \mathbf{A}_s + \mathbf{n}_k \\ &= \mathbf{H}_k \alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c s_c + \mathbf{H}_k \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k s_k + \sum_{j \neq k} \mathbf{H}_k \alpha_j \mathbf{p}_j s_j + \mathbf{n}_k \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Precoder Design: In overloaded scenario, the common precoder is computed as \mathbf{p}_c , which is the principal eigenvector (i.e., eigenvector associated to the largest eigenvalue) of the matrix $\sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{H}_k^H \mathbf{H}_k$. For the private precoders, they are computed based on Regularized Zero-forcer (RZF)

$$\mathbf{P}_{\text{RZF}} = \mathbf{H}^H (\mathbf{H} \mathbf{H}^H + \delta \mathbf{I})^{-1} \quad (13)$$

where $\delta = \frac{\text{trace}(\mathbf{H})}{\lambda}$, where λ is a scaling factor. The precoding vectors are normalized and weighted according to the power allocation coefficients.

In overloaded RSMA beamforming, the spatial distribution of the users plays an important role in the precoder design. The channels are defined as a random matrix with separable covariance, resulting in $\mathbf{H}_k = \mathbf{C}_{\text{Rx}}^{1/2} \mathbf{G}_k \mathbf{C}_{\text{Tx}}^{1/2}$, where the entries of the matrix \mathbf{G}_k are modeled as i.i.d. circularly symmetric Gaussian-distributed with zero mean and unit variance, with \mathbf{C}_{Tx} and \mathbf{C}_{Rx} denoting the transmit and receive covariance matrices. The \mathbf{C}_{Rx} is set as identity matrix, while \mathbf{C}_{Tx} is defined assuming a uniform linear array (ULA) with uniform antenna spacing. The elements of the covariance matrices are computed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{C}_{\text{Tx}(l,m)} &= \exp(j2\pi d_H(l-m)\sin(\psi)) \\ &\cdot \exp\left(-\frac{\sigma_\psi^2}{2}(2\pi d_H(l-m)\cos(\psi))^2\right) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

for $l, m = 1, \dots, N_T$, where ψ is the mean angle of arrival, d_H is the antenna spacing in multiples of the wavelength (set to 0.5), and σ_ψ^2 is the angular standard deviation (set to 10 deg).

It should be noted that precoding based on zero-forcing is the simplest scheme that can be implemented for RSMA. There are sophisticated algorithms like WMMSE [3], [13] that can eliminate the limitations observed in ZF precoders and offer higher system capacity, but the implementation of such algorithms are computationally intensive as the system size scales up.

Radiation Pattern: We look at the impact of private power allocation α_k^2 on the RSMA beamforming. As explained in Section II, the power allocation coefficients (α_c, α_k) of the common and private streams are governed by $\alpha_c^2 + \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k^2 = 1$. We restrict ourselves to the case of identical power allocation to all private streams (i.e., $\alpha_k^2 = \alpha^2$ for all k). Ideally, the common stream should be transmitted at a higher power than the intended private streams of the users. In Figure 19, the beamforming of all the streams are visualized for RSMA scenario with 4 users (with $N_R = 2$ antennas for each user) served by $N_T = 6$ antennas. The modulation scheme employed is QPSK, under linear channel conditions. For very low values of α^2 , the common stream is transmitted at high power compared to the private streams. The nulls are placed at respective users in order to eliminate inter-user interference. We also show the AWGN floor at 30dB (highest SNR in simulations) as a point of reference. The private streams are stronger at the respective users concerned, while the power of the interfering streams are lower than the noise floor. As the power allocation of private streams is increased, the pattern of the common stream moves closer to the noise floor, while the private streams increase in power level. At $\alpha^2 = 0.24$, there are instances where the private streams start to overlap with the main lobe of the intended private stream (for example: user 2). Thus, we set $\alpha^2 = 0.005$ to evaluate the performance of the receivers in overloaded RSMA.

FIGURE 19. Radiation pattern for the different power allocation coefficients ($N_T = 6$, $N_R = 2$, $K = 4$ users, $\psi = [-60^\circ, -30^\circ, 30^\circ, 60^\circ]$). The dotted lines (red) represent the user locations.

FIGURE 20. Channel estimation in overloaded RSMA ($N_T = 6$, $N_R = 2$, $K = 4$ users).

Channel Estimation: The NMSE performance of 1D-CNN and LS estimators in overloaded RSMA is as shown in Figure 20. The plot reveals that the neural network based channel estimation continues to outperform LS estimator. We use the same 1D-CNN neural network architecture of 128 kernels to train the 1D-CNN channel estimator in this overloaded scenario. It was previously observed in underloaded scenarios that the performance gain was marginal (Figure 9), but in overloaded scenarios, the gain from using 1D-CNN is substantial, especially for private channel estimation. For the given range of SNR, the LS estimator does not offer satisfactory NMSE performance, while the neural network is able to learn reliable estimates from the training dataset. The private channel estimate exhibits higher NMSE compared to common channel owing to the lower power allocation.

FIGURE 21. Symbol error rate in common (left) and private (right) with QPSK data symbols in overloaded RSMA ($N_T = 6$, $N_R = 2$, $K = 4$ users).

Symbol Detection: The symbol detection performance is depicted in Figure 21. The ML receiver which works with perfect CSIT is the lower bound for both the common and private stream SER. The private stream shows a significantly higher symbol error rate which is attributed to low power allocation. The LMMSE and SIC receivers operate with CSIR estimated via LS. The figure reveals that in overloaded scenarios, conventional detection schemes LMMSE/SIC perform poorly compared to data-driven receivers. The neural network schemes, namely RS-Net and Joint-Net, perform better than LMMSE/SIC for common stream, but fail to perform for private stream detection. Joint-Net is very close to ML in terms of common stream detection, but the pure black-box non-SIC approach is not able to detect the private stream. We increased the learning capacity of the neural network architecture (4 hidden layers of 256 neurons in each hidden layer), but the low power allocation to private stream makes it difficult for Joint-Net to learn sufficient knowledge to perform symbol detection. On the other hand, RS-Net+ which relies on the soft-estimate of the private message of the intended user performs better than RS-Net for common message detection. Among the neural network schemes, RS-Net+ is the only scheme that is able to perform symbol detection of the private message, and its performance

is closer to ML detection. This shows that neural network along with model knowledge incorporation (via soft-estimate causing intra-user interference) outperforms pure black-box approaches.

FIGURE 22. Symbol error rate in common (left) and private (right) with QPSK data symbols in overloaded RSMA. Solid lines represent for perfect CSIR, while dashed lines for CSIR estimated via LS, and dotted lines for CSIR estimated via 1D-CNN ($N_T = 6, N_R = 2, K = 4$ users).

Impact of CSIR error: The performance of conventional schemes strongly depend on the quality of channel estimation. In Figure 22, we analyze the impact of perfect CSIR (solid lines) and estimated CSIR (dashed lines). The top sub-plot reveals that LMMSE/SIC offer better performance when the channel is completely known. The errors in channel estimation easily propagate into symbol detection. As the LS estimator showed poor performance for private channel estimation (Figure 20), the performance of LMMSE/SIC suffers in private SER (dashed lines). On the other hand, neural network-based symbol detectors show that as long as test dataset does not deviate from training dataset, the symbol detection performance is not affected severely. In the bottom sub-plots of Figure 22, the SER curves for different neural network architectures are tested for different CSIR input. The solid lines represent perfect CSIR, dashed lines for CSIR estimated via LS, and dotted lines for CSIR estimated via 1D-CNN. The RS-Net architecture shows a flat behavior for common stream detection and records the highest SER in all cases. The RS-Net+ and Joint-Net show gradual degradation from 1D-CNN estimated CSIR to LS estimated

CSIR. However, for the private symbol detection, the difference between 1D-CNN estimated CSIR and perfect CSIR is marginal. But, the symbol error rate when models take LS estimated CSIR as input (dashed line) is very high (for all SNR) which is attributed to the poor private channel estimates. The RS-Net and Joint-Net architectures fail to learn to decode the private stream due to the low power allocation. But, RS-Net+ architecture learns sufficient information from the soft-estimate to improve common message detection, which further aids in private message detection.

The use of neural network based schemes, especially RS-Net+ architecture, has been shown to aid tremendously in overloaded RSMA scenarios. The performance gain observed in channel estimation scheme by using 1D-CNN aids in symbol detection. The pure black-box approaches offer reliable performance only for common stream detection which has majority of the power allocation, while performing poorly for private stream detection. The LMMSE/SIC receivers are sensitive to channel estimation via LS. The RS-Net+ architecture shows reliable performance owing to the 1D-CNN channel estimate and the soft-information provided.

VII. COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY ANALYSIS

In this section, we assess the computational complexity of the proposed data-driven detection schemes. As discussed earlier, our schemes do not require re-training on a frame-by-frame basis. Instead neural networks can be trained offline and then be used as long as the system scenario remains unchanged. Therefore, we will focus on the computational complexity in the prediction/inference (vs. training) phase. Table 2 summarizes the number of additions and multiplications needed by each detection scheme (proposed and benchmark) as a function of a number of system parameters. It should be noted, on one hand, that the complexity of the ML detector exhibits an exponential growth in the constellation size (B) and the number of streams to be detected (s). This is due to the fact that ML detection entails the computation of the log-likelihood functions for all the combinations of transmit symbols in the relevant streams (exhaustive search method). For multi-antenna users, we have $s = 3$ (common stream plus the private of both users⁶), whereas $s = 2$ (common stream plus the intended private stream) for single-antenna users. Also, it is worth noting that the RS-Net+ formulae include the overhead associated with the computation of the soft-estimate for the intended private message.

Figure 23 depicts the total number of operations (i.e., multiplications plus additions) required by all the detection schemes according to the formulae in Table 2. It is to be noted that the y-axis is in log-scale. For QPSK modulation (left sub-plot), the proposed NN-based detectors exhibit a much higher computational complexity than the conventional MMSE and SIC detectors (e.g., 50x increase in the case of RS-Net+). However, the SER of the NN-based detectors is substantially

⁶In multi-antenna users, owing to the additional degree of freedom Maximum Likelihood detector can be designed to detect all the streams.

TABLE 2. Computational complexity of the different detection schemes in the prediction phase.

Detector	Number of multiplications	Number of additions
ML	$3N_R N_T + (4N_R)B^s$	$3N_R(N_T - 1) + (2N_R)B^s + (N_R - 1)B^s$
LMMSE	$N_R^3 + N_R^2 + 2N_R + 2$	$(N_R^2 + N_R)(N_R - 1) + 2N_R + 1$
SIC	$\text{LMMSE} + N_R^3 + N_R^2 + 1$	$\text{LMMSE} + (N_R^2 + N_R)(N_R - 1)$
RS-Net	$2N_R N_i(N_T + 1) + L(N_i^2) + B(N_i)$	$L(N_i)$
RS-Net+	$3N_R + 3N_R N_i + (4N_R + N_i)N_i + B(N_i)$	$(5N_R - 1) + L(N_i)$
Joint-Net	$2N_R N_i(N_T + 1) + L(N_i^2) + 2B(N_i)$	$L(N_i)$

FIGURE 23. Computational complexity of all detection schemes for QPSK- (left) and 16QAM-modulated symbols ($N_R = 2$, $N_T = 6$, optimal N_i).

lower, and they are also more robust against non-linearities, as discussed in Section VI-VI-D. Out of the proposed NN-based detectors, RS-Net+ is the one exhibiting the lowest complexity despite the increased number of input signals it uses. When compared with Joint-Net, this follows from the fact that the optimal number of hidden layers and number of neurons per layer is lower. When compared with RS-Net, the RS-Net+ architecture involves separate processing of the input features (the soft symbol estimate and the channel response follow a separate path, see Figure 5) which also results in a more compact neural network. The total number of operations for RS-Net+ and ML schemes is comparable. As discussed in the previous section, ML outperforms RS-Net+ for linear channels. However, for non-linear ones, the ML detector collapses whereas RS-Net+ prevails. This motivates the use of NN-based schemes instead of conventional approaches. Finally, it should be noted that Joint-Net requires the highest number of operations owing to its denser architecture. Despite this, it exhibits a poor performance in several scenarios (e.g. with non-linear channels, or large constellations).

For 16QAM modulation (right subplot), most of the above considerations continue to be valid. However, due attention must be paid to the very noticeable increase of the computational complexity for the ML detector. This follows from the fact that the number of operations grows exponentially as the number of constellation points increases. On the contrary, the increase in operations for RS-Net+ is moderate. Owing of this, the complexity of RS-Net+ and ML detectors are now comparable. Alongside the lower SER of RS-Net+ in non-linear channels, its adoption is motivated in place of exhaustive search methods like the ML detector.

In the special section of overloaded RSMA (Section VI-VI-E), all the NN architectures were trained/ tested for different configurations of wider (more neurons in each hidden layer) and deeper networks (more hidden layers). The RS-Net and Joint-Net architectures did not show any improvement even for 4 hidden layers and 256 neurons in each hidden layer. On the contrary, the optimum architecture for RS-Net+ scheme involved 2 hidden layers with [64, 128] neurons respectively. This shows that a carefully designed neural network architecture is able to outperform deeper black-box approaches. The computational complexity of RS-Net+ is lower compared to RS-Net and Joint-Net in overloaded scenarios. It should be noted that an optimum maximum likelihood receiver for higher number of users in the system should involve exhaustive search of all the private streams and common stream (a total of 5 in the simulated overloaded scenario). This would be a limiting factor for the use of exhaustive search symbol detection as the number of streams in RSMA system increases, thus favoring the use of RS-Net+ scheme.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Deep learning architectures are promising approaches in order to improve the robustness of MIMO-RSMA receivers against model mismatches like noisy CSIT (resulting in imperfect precoders) and imperfect CSIR (due to non-linear channels). Out of all the analyzed architectures, RS-Net+ (which performs data-driven common symbol detection based on soft-estimates of the private symbol) stands out as the most reliable approach at higher order modulation schemes, and especially in overloaded RSMA. Conversely, pure black-box approaches like Joint-Net, exhibit poor performance and require higher computational complexity. The important advantages of data-driven channel estimators and symbol detectors are more apparent in non-linear channel conditions, where conventional schemes fail to provide satisfactory performance.

APPENDIX DERIVATION OF A SOFT ESTIMATE OF THE PRIVATE SYMBOL

The computation of soft estimate of the private symbol of the user is done using the received signal and channel state

information available at the receiver. Due to the design of orthogonal private precoders, the contribution from private streams of other users can be considered as null. We start the derivation from this perspective. Using the fact that $\mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{p}_j = \mathbf{0}$ for $j \neq k$ by construction of the precoders (see Section II), we can write the signal model at the k -th user as

$$\mathbf{y}_k = \mathbf{h}_c s_c + \mathbf{h}_k s_k + \mathbf{n}_k$$

where $\mathbf{h}_c = \alpha_c \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{p}_c$, $\mathbf{h}_k = \alpha_k \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{p}_k$ and where $\mathbf{n}_k \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_R})$. The problem here is to detect s_c by modeling s_k as a nuisance parameter, where \mathbf{h}_c and \mathbf{h}_k are deterministic and known, and where σ^2 is also known. Specifically, we model $s_k \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ so that $\mathbf{y}_k \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{h}_c s_c, \mathbf{C}_k)$ where $\mathbf{C}_k = \mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{h}_k^H + \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_R}$. The maximum likelihood estimator of s_c (following the ML detection as outlined in Section II-B) can be formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{s}_c &= \arg \min_{s_c} (\mathbf{y}_k - \mathbf{h}_c s_c)^H \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} (\mathbf{y}_k - \mathbf{h}_c s_c) \\ &= \frac{\mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \mathbf{y}_k}{\mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \mathbf{h}_c}. \end{aligned}$$

Now, using the matrix inversion lemma we see that

$$\mathbf{C}_k^{-1} = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \left(\mathbf{I}_{N_R} - \frac{1}{\sigma^2 + \|\mathbf{h}_k\|^2} \mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{h}_k^H \right) \quad (15)$$

and consequently we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \mathbf{h}_c &= \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \left(\frac{\mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{h}_c (\sigma^2 + \|\mathbf{h}_k\|^2) - \mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{h}_c}{\sigma^2 + \|\mathbf{h}_k\|^2} \right) \\ &= \frac{\|\mathbf{h}_c\|^2}{\sigma^2} \left(\frac{\sigma^2 + \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp \mathbf{h}_k}{\sigma^2 + \|\mathbf{h}_k\|^2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{P}_c^\perp = \mathbf{I}_{N_R} - \frac{\mathbf{h}_c \mathbf{h}_c^H}{\|\mathbf{h}_c\|^2}$ and, consequently

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{\mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \mathbf{h}_c} \\ &= \frac{\sigma^2}{\|\mathbf{h}_c\|^2} \left(1 + \frac{\mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}_c \mathbf{h}_k}{\sigma^2 + \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp \mathbf{h}_k} \right) \\ &= \sigma^2 \left(\frac{1}{\|\mathbf{h}_c\|^2} + \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{h}_c\|^2} \frac{\mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{h}_c}{\sigma^2 + \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp \mathbf{h}_k} \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{h}_c\|^2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

On the other hand, from (15) and (16) we have that

$$\mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \left(\mathbf{h}_c^H - \frac{1}{\sigma^2 + \|\mathbf{h}_k\|^2} \mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{h}_k^H \right) \quad (17)$$

and therefore, by multiplying the terms from (17) and (16), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{\mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \mathbf{h}_c} \mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \\ &= \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{h}_c\|^2} \mathbf{h}_c^H \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{\sigma^2 + \|\mathbf{h}_k\|^2} \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{h}_c\|^2} \mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{h}_k^H \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &+ \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{h}_c\|^2} \frac{\mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{h}_k}{\sigma^2 + \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp \mathbf{h}_k} \mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{P}_c \\ &- \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{h}_c\|^2} \frac{\mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}_c \mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{h}_k^H}{\sigma^2 + \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp \mathbf{h}_k} \frac{1}{\sigma^2 + \|\mathbf{h}_k\|^2} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

On the other hand, using $\mathbf{P}_c = \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{P}_c^\perp$ in the third term

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{\mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \mathbf{h}_c} \mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \\ &= \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{h}_c\|^2} \mathbf{h}_c^H - \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{h}_c\|^2} \\ &\quad \times \left(1 - \frac{\sigma^2 + \|\mathbf{h}_k\|^2}{\sigma^2 + \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp \mathbf{h}_k} + \frac{\mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}_c \mathbf{h}_k}{\sigma^2 + \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp \mathbf{h}_k} \right) \frac{\mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{h}_k^H}{\sigma^2 + \|\mathbf{h}_k\|^2} \\ &- \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{h}_c\|^2} \frac{\mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{h}_k}{\sigma^2 + \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp \mathbf{h}_k} \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp. \end{aligned}$$

where the second term is trivially zero, so that

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{s}_c &= \frac{\mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \mathbf{y}_k}{\mathbf{h}_c^H \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \mathbf{h}_c} \\ &= \frac{1}{\|\mathbf{h}_c\|^2} \mathbf{h}_c^H \left(\mathbf{y}_k - \frac{\mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp \mathbf{y}_k}{\sigma^2 + \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp \mathbf{h}_k} \mathbf{h}_k \right). \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

In the above expression, the quotient preceding \mathbf{h}_k inside the parenthesis can be regarded as a *soft* (LMMSE) estimate of the private symbol of the k -th user, s_k , when the common symbol s_c is estimated according to the maximum-likelihood principle, that is

$$\hat{s}_{\text{p-soft},k} = \frac{\mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp \mathbf{y}_k}{\sigma^2 + \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}_c^\perp \mathbf{h}_k} \quad (20)$$

with $\mathbf{h}_c = \alpha_c \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{p}_c$ and $\mathbf{h}_k = \alpha_k \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{p}_k$ as per the definitions in the beginning of this section.

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